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CHEMICAL DESUCKERING AS A MEANS FOR ENHANCED YIELD REALIZATION IN PLANTAIN (cv. nenthran)

Deepu Mathew and P.V. Habeeburrahman

Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Kerala Agricultural University, Tavanur – 679 573, Malappuram, Kerala
Email : deepuhort@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

Banana and plantain are important commercial fruit crops world wide. The production at global level is 97.5 million tones whereas, India, being the largest producer and consumer produces 13.9 million tones (23 per cent of global production). In India, the area under this crop is 0.42 million ha (NHB, 2008). Though this crop is originated in Indo-Malayan region, Kerala state of India holds a large number of unique and highly valuable landraces. Poovan, Kadali, Njalipooan, Palayamkodan, Chundillakannan, Kunnan, Karimkadali, Rasakadali, Chenkadali, Kali etc. are desert bananas and Chengalikkodan, Attunenthran and Manjeri Nenthran the widely cultivated plantains. Each of them varies widely in their taste, qualities, medicinal properties, pests and disease resistance, cultivation techniques and the environmental adaptations differ widely.

In general, members of the genus *Musa* vary widely in their reproductive capabilities. The present day seedless varieties are selected by man from the seeded ancestors (Simmonds and Shepherd, 1955). Still *Musa balbisiana* and common varieties such as Kunnan produce sexual seeds within the fruits. Similarly, in vegetative propagation also, present day banana varieties vary in the time of sucker initiation, number of suckers produced, vigour and maturity requirement of suckers, amount of nutrients diverted and negative effect of these suckers on bunch weight of the mother plant etc. It is well understood that in plantains, higher number of suckers increase the sink competition and thus reduce the bunch weight significantly (Obiefuna *et al.*, 1982, 1983; Robinson, 1995; Odeke *et al.*, 1999; Tenkouano *et al.*, 2007). Similarly, a negative correlation is observed between the sucker growth and the days taken to flowering and harvest (Tenkouano *et al.*, 2007). In plantains, the number of permitted suckers at bunching is optimized at two (Wassel *et al.*, 2000; Obiefuna *et al.*, 1983) and in Nenthran, only one or two suckers after the emergence of the bunch should be retained for higher yield (KAU, 2007). The maturity requirement of suckers intended for planting is only 3-4 months whereas in small table type bananas it is 4-5 months. This shows that in Nenthran variety, suckers that emerge before bunching should be removed and the number should not exceed the stipulated two.

Farmers practice the desuckering by labour intensive stamping process of emerging pseudostem at ground level, both in table bananas and plantains. But the growing point is well protected at the centre of the underground sucker and this will not be affected by the stamping process. Ultimately, this process results in diversion of more carbohydrates by the suckers to compensate the loss and to regenerate with more power. To solve this problem, an experiment was conducted by Krishi Vigyan Kendra (Kerala Agricultural University) with the objective of standardizing a simple methodology for eradication of early emerged suckers that is less labour and cost demanding and quick resulting but with no side effects on the mother plant or on the size and quality of the bunch.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The entire experiments were conducted during 2007-08 at the fields of 10 selected farmers of Malappuram district, Kerala state, India, as part of the On Farm Tests funded by Indian Council of Agricultural Research. From every field, fifteen healthy plants each and at seven months stage were selected for the study.

Five plants from every field were subjected to stamping, five for chemical desuckering and remaining 5 were maintained as control. For chemical desuckering, the suckers were cut horizontally at 15-20 cm height, a depression was made at the centre of the cut surface and kerosene was directly poured at this point. The volume of kerosene used was adjusted with the diameter and height of the pseudostem. If the used volume was not sufficient, protrusion of the growing bud was observed within 2-3 days. In such cases, the treatment was repeated to decide the minimum volume required for killing the growing bud. This volume was standardized through regression analysis of pseudostem parameters using the MINITAB statistical software, v.11. Treatment effects on reemergence of pseudostem and yield were analyzed statistically and the significance was compared at 0.05 per cent level using the JMP (SAS Institute) statistical software, v.7.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the desuckering experiments indicated that both stamping off as well as chemical desuckering had no negative effects on the mother plants. However, no visible morphological variations such as number of leaves, girth of pseudostems were observed between the treatments. There was statistically significant variation in the regeneration of the suckers that were stamped or treated with kerosene. When the regeneration was recorded 60 days after the process, 48.3 per cent of the stamped suckers were found to have restarted the growth whereas in case of suckers treated with kerosene, the regeneration was only 12.1 per cent. The only reported methodology for chemical desuckering in banana is through the use of herbicide 2, 4-D at 2 per cent concentration (Singh *et al.*, 2000; Eckstein *et al.*, 2000; Singh and Pathak, 1997; Singh and Pathak, 2000; Chundawat and Patel, 1992). Though 2, 4-D is reported to be effective to bring sucker mortality, kerosene got the additional advantages of acceptability in organic farming, easiness in procurement and less costly. Apart from these, being a herbicide, 2, 4-D got the large disadvantage of giving negative effect on the mother plant at supra-optimal concentrations (Singh *et al.*, 2000).

The desuckering and method of desuckering had profound effect on the bunch weight of Nenthran plantain. The non-desuckered plants yielded a bunch weight of 7.83 kg whereas desuckering through stamping was effective to increase this to 8.68 kg. Many previous studies on desuckering through stamping (Odeke *et al.*, 1999) have shown that this process got the capability to increase the bunch weight. However, the non-desuckering was found to result in higher total yield due to increase in number of bunches. But the bunch as well as finger sizes will not be market acceptable (Obiefuna *et al.*, 1982). Few other mechanical procedures such as digging with spade or gouging tool was also found to increase the bunch weight (Tadros *et al.*, 1983). But the damage caused to the roots and suckers was found to destabilize the mother plant on bunch maturity. Chemical desuckering using kerosene was found to increase the mean bunch weight to 9.25 kg. This bunch weight is 18.2 per cent higher over the non-desuckered control and 6.65 per cent over the stamping.

The volume of kerosene required (x) was a function of the pseudostem size, $x = -4.61 + 0.317y + 0.266z$ where, y and z were pseudostem height and diameter at the point of beheading (cm) respectively. Thus from this experiment, it was clear that chemical desuckering in plantain is an efficient and cost effective organic strategy with no negative effects on mother plant for realizing higher bunch weight.

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